

FUNKSIONAL LINGVISTIKA DOIRASIDA TEJAMKORLIK TAMOYILI**Fayzullayeva Nigina Sur'at qizi**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu ilmiy maqola til evolutsiyasi va uning tejamkorlik tamoyilidagi ifodalanishi hamda tilshunoslik va kommunikatsiya tizimlarida qanday aks etishi masalalarini ko'rib chiqadi. Nazariy tahlil va empirik tadqiqotlar asosida til tuzilishining murakkablik darajasi, tejamkorlik printsipi va til evolutsiyasining ijtimoiy, madaniy va texnologik omillarga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi – til evolutsiyasidagi tejamkorlik tamoyilining asosiy mexanizmlari va uning turli til tizimlarida aks etish shakllarini aniqlash, shuningdek, tilning rivojlanishidagi optimallashtirish jarayonlarini ko'rsatishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: til evolutsiyasi, tejamkorlik tamoyili, tilshunoslik, nazariy tahlil, empirik tadqiqotlar, kommunikatsiya, optimallashtirish.

THE PRINCIPLE OF ECONOMY IN THE FRAMEWORK OF FUNCTIONAL LINGUISTICS

Abstract. This scientific article considers the issues of language evolution and its expression in the principle of economy and how it is reflected in linguistics and communication systems. Based on theoretical analysis and empirical research, the level of complexity of language structure, the principle of economy and the influence of language evolution on social, cultural and technological factors are analyzed. The main purpose of the article is to identify the main mechanisms of the principle of economy in language evolution and the forms of its reflection in various language systems, as well as to show the optimization processes in language development.

Keywords: language evolution, economy principle, linguistics, theoretical analysis, empirical research, communication, optimization.

ПРИНЦИП ЭКОНОМИИ В ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ

Аннотация. В данной научной статье рассматриваются вопросы эволюции языка и ее проявления в принципе экономии, а также то, как она отражается в лингвистике и системах коммуникации. На основе теоретического анализа и эмпирических исследований анализируется уровень сложности структуры языка, принцип экономии, а также влияние на эволюцию языка социальных, культурных и технологических факторов. Основная цель статьи — выявить основные механизмы принципа экономии в развитии языка и формы его отражения в различных языковых системах, а также продемонстрировать процессы оптимизации в развитии языка.

Ключевые слова: эволюция языка, принцип экономии, лингвистика, теоретический анализ, эмпирические исследования, коммуникация, оптимизация.

Kirish. Tilshunoslikda til tizimini o'rganishning turli nazariy yondashuvlari mavjud bo'lib, ularning orasida funksional lingvistika muhim o'rin tutadi. Ushbu yo'nalish tilning tuzilishidan ko'ra, uning asosiy vazifalari va amaliy jihatlariga e'tibor qaratadi. Funksional lingvistika tilda sodir bo'ladigan o'zgarishlarni izohlashda samaradorlik va kommunikativ qulaylik tamoyillarini asosiy mezon sifatida ko'radi. Ushbu maqolada funksional lingvistika doirasida tejamkorlik tamoyili qanday namoyon bo'lishi va bu tamoyil tilning fonetik, morfologik, sintaktik hamda pragmatik darajalarida qanday aks etishi tahlil qilinadi.

Funksional lingvistika va uning asosiy tamoyillari. Funksional lingvistika til tizimining qulaylik, iqtisod va samaradorlik printsiplariga asoslanishini ta'kidlaydi. André Martinet tomonidan rivojlantirilgan funksional tilshunoslik nazariyasiga ko'ra, til doimiy ravishda yanada qulayroq va samaraliroq kommunikatsiyaga erishish uchun optimallashtiriladi (Martinet, 1955).

Tilning rivojlanishida ikkita asosiy omil muhim sanaladi:

1. Aniqlik tamoyili (principe de clarté) – til aniq va tushunarli bo'lishi kerak, chunki ma'lumot uzatilishi samarali bo'lishi lozim.

2. Tejamkorlik tamoyili (principe d'économie) – ortiqcha resurslarni tejashga intilish orqali til murakkab tuzilmalar o'rniga soddaroq va qulayroq shakllarni afzal ko'radi.

Asosiy qism. Mazkur ikki tamoyil o'rtasidagi **muvozanat** til o'zgarishlari va evolutsiyasining asosiy harakatlantiruvchi kuchlaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Tejamkorlik tamoyili va uning til tizimidagi aks etishi. fonetik darajada tejamkorlik.

Fonetik jihatdan til tizimi minimal energiya sarfi bilan optimal muloqotni ta'minlashga intiladi. Bunda *assimilyatsiya, eliziya, reduksiya va talaffuzdagi qisqarishlar* muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Masalan:

Ingliz tilida “going to” iborasining og'zaki nutqda “gonna” shaklida aytilishi.

O'zbek tilida “kelayapman” so'zining og'zaki nutqda “kelyapman” yoki hatto “kelyamman” tarzida qisqarishi.

Bu holatlar fonetik iqtisod (economy of articulation) tamoyiliga asoslanib, inson miyasining **kamroq energiya sarf qilib, ko'proq ma'lumot yetkazish** tendensiyasiga mos keladi.

Morfologik darajada tejamkorlik. Morfologiya darajasida tejamkorlik **grammatik qisqartirishlar, unifikatsiya va affikslarning polifunksionalligi** orqali aks etadi. Masalan:

Ingliz tilida **Old English** davrida otlarda ko'plikni ifodalovchi bir necha shakl bo'lsa (masalan, "oxen" kabi nostandart shakllar), zamonaviy ingliz tilida deyarli barcha ko'plik shakllari "-s" yordamida ifodalanadi. Bu morfologik iqtisod natijasidir.

O'zbek tilida **kelishik qo'shimchalari ko'p vazifali bo'lib, bir so'z tarkibida turli grammatik ma'nolarni berishi** mumkin. Masalan, "-ning" qo'shimchasi egalik, kelishik va bog'lovchi funksiya bajaradi (*Farhodning kitobi* – egalik, *Farhodning kitobini* – bog'lovchi). Bu esa til tizimida ortiqcha grammatik birliklar paydo bo'lishining oldini oladi.

Sintaktik darajada tejamkorlik. Til sintaktik jihatdan ham tejamkor bo'lishga intiladi. Bu, asosan, **gap tuzilmasining ixchamlanishi va ortiqcha bo'laklarning tushib qolishi** orqali amalga oshiriladi. Masalan:

Ingliz tilida **nisbiy ergash gaplar** ko'pincha tushirib qoldiriladi: "*The book (that) I read was interesting*". Bu yerda "*that*" so'zining tushirilishi sintaktik iqtisodning natijasidir.

O'zbek tilida esa **gap qisqarishi va birikmalar orqali sintaktik qulaylik yaratiladi**: masalan, "*Men kitobni o'qib bo'ldim*" (uzun shakl) o'rniga "*Men kitobni o'qidim*" shaklida aytiladi.

Pragmatik darajada tejamkorlik. Pragmatik jihatdan tejamkorlik **nutqda ma'lumotning ortiqcha bo'lishini oldini olishga** asoslanadi. Bunda asosiy omil **Graysning Hamkorlik prinsipi** bo'lib, unga ko'ra, suhbatdoshlardan biri muloqot davomida minimal so'zlash orqali **aniqlik va samaradorlikni saqlab qolishi lozim** (Grice, 1975). Masalan:

Suhbatda qisqa va aniq javoblar afzal ko'riladi:

Savol: "Siz universitetga bordingizmi?"

Javob: "Ha" (uzun shaklda: "Ha, men universitetga bordim" deb javob berish ortiqcha bo'lishi mumkin).

Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda ham qisqartmalar va belgilar orqali **axborot uzatish soddalashtiriladi**: masalan, ingliz tilida "*LOL*" (Laughing Out Loud), o'zbek tilida esa "*kk*" (kulish) kabi qisqartmalarining qo'llanilishi.

Xulosa. Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish joizki, funksional lingvistika tamoyillariga ko'ra, til samaradorlik va tejamkorlik asosida rivojlanadi. Tejamkorlik tamoyili tilning barcha darajalarida – fonetik, morfologik, sintaktik va pragmatik jihatlarda namoyon bo'lib, muloqotni qulay va samarali qiladi. Fonetik jihatdan tovushlarning qisqarishi, morfologik jihatdan qo'shimchalarning unifikatsiyasi, sintaktik jihatdan gap tuzilmasining ixchamlanishi, pragmatik jihatdan esa minimal nutq orqali aniqlik saqlanishi – bularning barchasi til tizimidagi iqtisod tamoyili asosida shakllangan hodisalardir.

Ushbu tamoyilning amaliy qo'llanilishi sun'iy intellekt va tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash sohalarida ham muhim bo'lib, tilni kodlash, tarjima qilish va algoritmik qayta ishlash jarayonlarida samaradorlikni oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Shu sababli, funksional lingvistika nuqtayi nazaridan tejamkorlik tamoyili nafaqat tilshunoslik, balki texnologiya va kommunikatsiya sohaları uchun ham dolzarb hisoblanadi.

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